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Interactive and indirect effects of trait impulsivity facets on body mass index

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Abstract

Impulsivity is a personality trait that may be a risk factor for overweight and obesity. Increasing evidence suggests, however, that only specific facets of impulsivity are associated with eating- and weight-related variables. Moreover, there seem to be interactive effects such that eating-related self-regulation is low when more than one impulsivity facet is elevated. Finally, the effect of impulsivity on body weight appears to be indirect, that is, is mediated by eating behaviors. In the current study, 790 adults (83% female, 80% students) completed a short form of the *Barratt Impulsiveness Scale* and the *Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting Scale* online and reported their current height and weight. Scores on attentional and motor impulsivity were interactively associated with perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation: Higher attentional impulsivity was associated with lower perceived self-regulatory success at high levels of motor impulsivity, but not at low levels of motor impulsivity. A moderated mediation model revealed an indirect effect of attentional impulsivity on body mass index (BMI) via perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation at high, but not low levels of motor impulsivity. Non-planning impulsivity was unrelated to perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation and BMI. Results support previous findings such that attentional and motor impulsivity are interactively associated with eating- and weight-related measures. Specifically, eating-related self-regulation is low when both attentional and motor impulsivity levels are high. Moreover, results further support that self-reported trait impulsivity is not directly related to BMI, but indirectly via eating behaviors as potential mediators.

Keywords

Impulsivity; Barratt Impulsiveness Scale; Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting Scale; Body mass index; Moderated mediation

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Introduction

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Impulsivity refers to a predisposition toward rapid, unplanned actions without regard to possible negative consequences of these actions (Moeller, Barratt, Dougherty, Schmitz, & Swann, 2001). High impulsivity levels have been suggested to contribute to overweight and obesity (Guerrieri, Nederkoorn, & Jansen, 2008). For example, obese children and adults reacted more impulsively than normal-weight participants did in behavioral tasks (e.g., go/no-go, stop signal, or delay discounting tasks; Fields, Sabet, & Reynolds, 2013; Mobbs, Iglesias, Golay, & Van der Linden, 2011; Nederkoorn, Braet, Van Eijs, Tanghe, & Jansen, 2006; Nederkoorn, Smulders, Havermans, Roefs, & Jansen, 2006; Weller, Cook, Avsar, & Cox, 2008; Wirt, Hundsdörfer, Schreiber, Keszyüs, & Steinacker, 2014). Similarly, obese children and adults reported higher impulsivity than normal-weight participants did using questionnaire measures (Mobbs, Crépin, Thiéry, Golay, & Van der Linden, 2010; Nederkoorn, Braet, et al., 2006; Rydén et al., 2003). Furthermore, higher impulsivity (lower motor response inhibition in particular) prospectively predicted weight gain or lower weight loss in children (Nederkoorn, Jansen, Mulkens, & Jansen, 2007; Reinert, Po'e, & Barkin, 2013).

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Although this converging evidence exists, findings are inconsistent. For example, scores on impulsivity measures were unrelated to body weight in several studies in children and adults (e.g., Fields et al., 2013; Hendrick, Luo, Zhang, & Li, 2012; Koritzky, Yechiam, Bukay, & Milman, 2012; Loeber et al., 2012; Verdejo-García et al., 2010). In other studies, impulsivity was associated with body weight or weight gain, but only as a function of moderating variables such as responsiveness to food cues in children and adults (Houben, Nederkoorn, & Jansen, 2014; Meule & Platte, 2016; Nederkoorn, Coelho, Guerrieri, Houben, & Jansen, 2012; Nederkoorn, Houben, Hofmann, Roefs, & Jansen, 2010).

25 These inconsistent findings may partly be explained by small effect sizes of the
26 relationship between impulsivity and body mass index (BMI) and the fact that only specific
27 facets of impulsivity are associated with body weight (Emery & Levine, in press; Meule &
28 Blechert, 2016; Mobbs et al., 2010). For example, one of the most widely used self-report
29 measures for the assessment of impulsivity, the *Barratt Impulsiveness Scale* (BIS; Stanford et
30 al., 2009), comprises three subscales representing *attentional impulsivity* (i.e., inability to
31 focus attention or concentrate), *motor impulsivity* (i.e., acting spontaneously or without
32 thinking), and *non-planning impulsivity* (i.e., lack of future orientation or forethought; Patton,
33 Stanford, & Barratt, 1995). Emerging evidence suggests that particularly attentional
34 impulsivity is associated with self-reported eating behaviors and body weight (Meule, 2013;
35 Meule & Blechert, 2016). In addition, elevated motor impulsivity has been reported in eating
36 disorder patients who binge eat (Claes, Nederkoorn, Vandereycken, Guerrieri, & Vertommen,
37 2006; Nasser, Gluck, & Geliebter, 2004; Rosval et al., 2006).

38 Based on these observations, it has been speculated that there might be interactive
39 effects between attentional and motor impulsivity in relation to eating behaviors and body
40 weight. Specifically, high attentional impulsivity may be related to moderate overeating
41 through reward-sensitive mechanisms, but may be particularly crucial (e.g., clinically
42 relevant) in combination with high motor impulsivity, indicating low inhibitory control
43 (Meule, 2013). Indeed, such interactive effects between impulsivity facets have been found in
44 recent studies. Higher scores on attentional impulsivity in combination with higher scores on
45 motor impulsivity related to higher percent body fat and self-reported binge eating severity in
46 female students (Meule & Platte, 2015), intake of sweet foods in the laboratory in female
47 students (Kakoschke, Kemps, & Tiggemann, 2015), and addiction-like eating in obese adults
48 (Meule, de Zwaan, & Müller, 2017). To conclude, it appears that when both attentional and
49 motor impulsivity levels are high, individuals exhibit low eating-related self-regulation.

50 Another consideration when examining associations between impulsivity and obesity
51 is how an impulsive personality translates into higher body weight. Specifically, as
52 impulsivity is a construct that does not cover energy intake or expenditure, it is implausible
53 that it affects fat mass directly. Higher impulsivity can only lead to higher body weight
54 through mediating mechanisms, for example, eating behavior. Accordingly, some studies
55 showed that the relationship between trait impulsivity and body weight was mediated by
56 eating-related measures such as frequent food cravings, low perceived self-regulatory success
57 in weight regulation, and addiction-like eating (e.g., Meule & Blechert, 2017; Murphy, Stojek,
58 & MacKillop, 2014; VanderBroek-Stice, Stojek, Beach, & MacKillop, 2017). Importantly,
59 this indirect effect was observed even in the absence of a directly observable relationship
60 between impulsivity and body weight (i.e., total effect).

61 Recently, we sought to combine these findings in a sample of children and adolescents
62 by examining the interactive effect between attentional and motor impulsivity (moderation)
63 and the indirect effect of impulsivity on body weight (mediation) in one model (moderated
64 mediation; Meule, Hofmann, Weghuber, & Blechert, 2016). It was found that motor
65 impulsivity moderated the indirect effect of attentional impulsivity on BMI through perceived
66 self-regulatory success in weight regulation. Specifically, there was an indirect effect of
67 higher attentional impulsivity on higher BMI through lower perceived self-regulatory success
68 in weight regulation, but this indirect effect was only present in children and adolescents who
69 had high motor impulsivity levels.

70 In the current study, we sought to replicate this model in an adult sample. Specifically,
71 it was expected that there would be an indirect effect of attentional impulsivity on BMI
72 through perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation as a function of motor
73 impulsivity: higher attentional impulsivity was expected to indirectly relate to higher BMI via

- 74 lower perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation, but only in individuals with high
- 75 motor impulsivity (Figure 1).

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Methods

77 *Participants and procedure*

78 Data were collected in an online survey at www.unipark.com. Participants were
79 recruited via e-mails to student mailing lists at several German and Austrian universities, via
80 social networks, and via a posting on the website of the German version of Psychology
81 Today. The study included a short form of the BIS (BIS-15), the *Perceived Self-Regulatory*
82 *Success in Dieting Scale* (PSRS), and other questionnaires. Participants also indicated their
83 current height and weight, among other sociodemographic data. Every question required a
84 response in order to continue. Completion of the study lasted approximately eight to ten
85 minutes. Three × 50 € were raffled among participants who completed the survey. The
86 website was visited 1396 times and $n = 805$ participants completed the entire set of questions.
87 Twelve participants were excluded from analyses because they answered questions too
88 rapidly (total completion time of less than five minutes). Three participants, who reported a
89 very young or old age (12, 14 and 87 years old), were excluded from analyses, leaving a final
90 sample size of $n = 790$.

91 Most participants were women (82.9%, $n = 655$) and had German (81.3%, $n = 642$) or
92 Austrian (14.2%, $n = 112$) citizenship. The majority of participants were students (79.6%, $n =$
93 629), employed (11.4%, $n = 90$), or pupils (4.70%, $n = 37$). Mean age was $M = 24.7$ years (SD
94 = 6.79). Mean BMI was $M = 22.3$ kg/m² ($SD = 3.93$). Seventy-six participants (9.60%) were
95 underweight (BMI < 18.5 kg/m²), 583 participants (73.9%) had normal weight (BMI = 18.5-
96 24.9 kg/m²), 92 participants (11.7%) were overweight (BMI = 25.0-29.9 kg/m²), and 38
97 participants (4.80%) were obese (BMI ≥ 30.00 kg/m²).

98 *Measures*

99 *Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting Scale (PSRS)*. The PSRS (Meule,
100 Papiés, & Kübler, 2012) is a three-item questionnaire for measuring how successful
101 individuals are in watching their weight and in losing weight, and how difficult it is for them
102 to stay in shape. Response categories are anchored *not successful/not difficult* and *very*
103 *successful/very difficult* (scored from 1 to 7). Thus, higher values indicate higher perceived
104 self-regulatory success in weight regulation. Internal consistency was $\alpha = .696$ in the current
105 study.

106 *Barratt Impulsiveness Scale – short form (BIS-15)*. The BIS-15 (Meule, Vögele, &
107 Kübler, 2011; Spinella, 2007) is a 15-item short form of the BIS-11 for measuring trait
108 impulsivity. Response categories range from *rarely/never* to *almost always/always* (scored
109 from 1 to 4). Thus, higher values indicate higher impulsivity. Internal consistencies were $\alpha =$
110 $.670$ (attentional), $\alpha = .734$ (motor), and $\alpha = .794$ (non-planning) in the current study.

111 *Data analyses*

112 Linear regression analyses were used to examine moderation and mediation effects
113 with PROCESS for SPSS (Hayes, 2013). Specifically, a moderated mediation model (model
114 no. 7 in PROCESS) was tested, in which scores on attentional and motor impulsivity and their
115 two-way interaction were used as predictors of PSRS scores (i.e., the mediating variable) and,
116 in a second regression, attentional impulsivity and PSRS scores as predictors of BMI (Figure
117 1). Predictor variables were mean-centered before calculating the product terms. A significant
118 interaction was followed up with simple slopes analysis at high (+1SD) and low (-1SD) values
119 of the moderator variable (Hayes, 2013). As we had directional hypotheses about the presence
120 of indirect effects of attentional impulsivity on BMI through perceived self-regulatory success
121 in weight regulation as a function of motor impulsivity, indirect effects were evaluated with
122 90% bias-corrected confidence intervals based on 10,000 bootstrap samples. When the
123 confidence interval does not contain zero, this means that the indirect effect can be considered

124 statistically significant (Hayes, 2013). Furthermore, the index of moderated mediation was
125 used as a formal test of moderated mediation (Hayes, 2015). When the confidence interval for
126 this index does not contain zero, this means that the presence of indirect effects depends on
127 the value of a moderating variable. Because non-planning impulsivity was associated with
128 PSRS scores in children and adolescents (Meule et al., 2016), it was included in the model as
129 covariate. Furthermore, sex was included as covariate because of the unequal sex distribution
130 in the current study.

131 Results

132 Descriptive statistics of and correlations between variables are depicted in Table 1.
133 Scores on the PSRS were negatively correlated with BMI and with attentional impulsivity.
134 Subscale scores of the BIS-15 were positively correlated with each other.

135 Attentional impulsivity negatively related to PSRS scores (Table 2). Moreover,
136 attentional and motor impulsivity interactively related to PSRS scores (Table 2). Examination
137 of the nature of this interaction revealed that attentional impulsivity negatively related to
138 PSRS scores, but only at high levels of motor impulsivity and not at low levels of motor
139 impulsivity (Figure 2). Furthermore, PSRS scores negatively related to BMI (Table 2). The
140 index of moderated mediation was significant (index = 0.02, $SE = 0.01$, 90% CI [0.001,
141 0.03]). Testing the indirect effect of BIS-15 scores on BMI revealed that PSRS scores
142 mediated the association between attentional impulsivity and BMI, but only at medium and
143 high levels of motor impulsivity and not at low levels of motor impulsivity (Table 3). Being
144 female was associated with lower PSRS scores and BMI. Non-planning impulsivity was not
145 associated with PSRS scores and BMI (Table 2).

146 The moderated mediation model can be summarized as follows: Higher attentional
147 impulsivity was associated with lower perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation,
148 particularly when motor impulsivity levels were also high. Motor impulsivity also moderated

149 the indirect effect of attentional impulsivity on BMI: Although there was no directly
150 observable association between attentional impulsivity and BMI, there was an indirect
151 association between attentional impulsivity and BMI via perceived self-regulatory success in
152 weight regulation, but only at medium and high levels of motor impulsivity.

153 Discussion

154 The current study sought to replicate interactive effects between and indirect effects of
155 two impulsivity facets on BMI. In accordance with prior findings in children and adolescents
156 (Meule et al., 2016), an interaction between attentional and motor impulsivity was found.
157 Higher attentional impulsivity in combination with high levels of motor impulsivity related to
158 lower perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation. In turn, lower perceived self-
159 regulatory success related to higher BMI. Although attentional impulsivity scores were
160 uncorrelated with BMI, an indirect effect was found: higher attentional impulsivity was
161 indirectly associated with BMI via lower perceived self-regulatory success at medium and
162 high levels of motor impulsivity, but not when motor impulsivity was low. Thus, results are in
163 line with previous findings that showed similar interactive effects between attentional and
164 motor impulsivity when predicting eating-related variables (Kakoschke et al., 2015; Meule et
165 al., 2017; Meule et al., 2016; Meule & Platte, 2015) and with findings that showed indirect
166 effects of impulsivity facets on BMI in the absence of a direct association (Meule & Blechert,
167 2017; Meule et al., 2016; Murphy et al., 2014).

168 In line with previous proposals (Meule, 2013), the interaction between attentional and
169 motor impulsivity suggests that while high attentional impulsivity relates to a higher
170 susceptibility to overeat, this susceptibility may only become clinically relevant (e.g.,
171 resulting in overweight) when motor impulsivity is also high. In other words, a low motor
172 impulsivity may compensate for a high attentional impulsivity, thus attenuating the risk for
173 regular overeating and gaining weight. Although the current results provide initial insights

174 into the mediators of the relationship between attentional and motor impulsivity with body
175 weight (here: low perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation), future studies are
176 needed that further examine the mediators (e.g., cognitive mechanisms) that link these
177 impulsivity facets with eating behaviors.

178 In contrast to our previous study in children and adolescents (Meule et al., 2016), non-
179 planning impulsivity was unrelated to PSRS scores, which may be due to age differences
180 between samples. For example, it may be that the items of the non-planning impulsivity
181 subscale, which refer to planning for the future (e.g., job-related), differently apply to children
182 and adolescents as opposed to adults. Although non-planning impulsivity has occasionally
183 been reported to be associated with eating-related self-report measures (e.g., Van
184 Koningsbruggen, Stroebe, & Aarts, 2013; Yeomans, Leitch, & Mobini, 2008) or responses to
185 food cues (e.g., Meule & Platte, 2016; van der Laan, Barendse, Viergever, & Smeets, 2016),
186 we would argue that the current findings are in line with previous studies showing that
187 attentional and motor impulsivity are most consistently associated with self-reported eating
188 behaviors (Meule, 2013).

189 While the current study focused on three facets of self-reported trait impulsivity, other
190 aspects such as motor response inhibition or delay discounting have been related to eating
191 behaviors (e.g., binge eating) and overweight as well (Manwaring, Green, Myerson, Strube, &
192 Wilfley, 2011; Mobbs et al., 2011; Nederkoorn, Smulders, et al., 2006; Weller et al., 2008).
193 Although some evidence suggests that scores on the BIS, and particularly on its attentional
194 and motor impulsivity subscales, are associated with lower motor response inhibition as
195 assessed with behavioral tasks (Aichert et al., 2012; Lange & Eggert, 2015; Meule, in press)
196 and that non-planning impulsivity scores and delay discounting are associated with activation
197 of overlapping brain areas (van der Laan et al., 2016), these associations have been small and
198 inconsistent. Thus, future research may investigate how other operationalizations of

199 impulsivity can be integrated into the model proposed in the current study. For example,
200 while some behavioral impulsivity measures may be used as an equivalent to BIS subscales,
201 others may represent distinct impulsivity aspects that may interact with—or independently
202 explain additional variance over and above—BIS subscales.

203 Interpretation of results is limited by the cross-sectional nature of the study and, thus,
204 the putative causal relationships between variables (i.e., impulsivity → self-regulatory success
205 in weight regulation → BMI) need to be established with longitudinal designs. However, as
206 self-reported impulsivity is considered a stable trait (e.g., as indicated by high retest-reliability
207 of the BIS; Meule et al., 2015; Stanford et al., 2009) and has been found to prospectively
208 predict weight gain (e.g., Meule & Platte, 2016; Nederkoorn et al., 2010), the hypothetical
209 causal directions tested in the current study are probable. A second limitation is the reliance
210 on self-report, which is vulnerable to bias. For example, it is known that self-reported height
211 is usually overestimated and weight is underestimated (Connor Gorber, Tremblay, Moher, &
212 Gorber, 2007). However, it has also been reported that although these discrepancies exist,
213 values are usually sufficiently accurate for analyses (Bowman & DeLucia, 1992; Pursey,
214 Burrows, Stanwell, & Collins, 2014). Finally, the present findings are based on a sample of
215 predominantly German, female students. Although they replicate results found in
216 predominantly Austrian children and adolescents (Meule et al., 2016), they may not apply to
217 older individuals or to people with another cultural and educational background.

218 Notwithstanding these limitations, the current study lends further support for three
219 important methodological considerations that need to be taken into account when examining
220 the role of impulsivity for overweight and obesity. First, only specific facets (e.g., attentional
221 and motor impulsivity) appear to relate to low eating-related self-regulation while others (e.g.,
222 non-planning impulsivity) do not or, at least, play a minor role in this context. Second, these
223 impulsivity facets interact with each other when predicting eating-related measures.

224 Specifically, eating-related self-regulation (e.g., perceived self-regulatory success in weight
225 regulation) is low when more than one impulsivity facet (e.g., both attentional and motor
226 impulsivity) is elevated. Finally, the association between impulsivity and BMI is mediated by
227 eating-related variables (e.g., perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation).

228 Importantly, in contrast to widely held beliefs about mediation testing, it is indeed possible to
229 establish such indirect effects in the absence of a total effect (Zhao, Lynch, & Chen, 2010).

230 Thus, it appears that impulsivity has an indirect effect on BMI that can be observed even in
231 the absence of a direct correlation.

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Table 1

Descriptive statistics of and correlations between variables

<i>N</i> = 790	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.
1. Body mass index (kg/m ²)	22.3	3.93	-	-.401*	.037	.060	.031
2. Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting	12.3	3.87		-	-.177*	-.054	-.031
3. Attentional impulsivity	9.79	2.71			-	.243*	.194*
4. Motor impulsivity	10.6	2.62				-	.413*
5. Non-planning impulsivity	10.6	3.07					-

**p* < .001

Table 2

Results from linear regression analyses with impulsivity scores predicting perceived self-regulatory success in dieting and body mass

<i>N</i> = 790	Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting			Body mass index (kg/m ²)		
	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>
Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting	-	-	-	-0.46	0.03	< .001
Attentional impulsivity	-0.21	0.05	< .001	-0.05	0.05	.337
Motor impulsivity	0.02	0.06	.801	-	-	-
Attentional × motor impulsivity	-0.04	0.02	.049	-	-	-
Non-planning impulsivity	-0.03	0.05	.498	-0.01	0.04	.862
Sex (1 = male, 2 = female)	-2.08	0.36	< .001	-2.22	0.34	< .001

Table 3

Conditional indirect effects of attentional impulsivity (independent variable) on body mass index (outcome variable) via perceived self-regulatory success in dieting (mediator) at different levels of motor impulsivity (moderator)

Values of the moderator	Effect (bootstrap estimate)	SE (bootstrap estimate)	90% bias-corrected bootstrap CI
Low motor impulsivity (-1 <i>SD</i>)	0.06	0.04	-0.001, 0.12
Medium motor impulsivity (mean)	0.10	0.03	0.06, 0.14
High motor impulsivity (+1 <i>SD</i>)	0.14	0.04	0.09, 0.21

Figure captions

Figure 1. Moderated mediation model. Scores on attentional and motor impulsivity and their interaction were used as predictors of perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation. Scores on attentional impulsivity and perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation were used as predictors of body mass index. Scores on non-planning impulsivity and sex were used as covariates. Attentional and motor impulsivity interactively related to perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation (also see Figure 2). Perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation, in turn, negatively related to body mass index (also see Table 2). There was no direct effect of attentional impulsivity on body mass index, but an indirect effect of attentional impulsivity on body mass index through low perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation, which was particularly evident at high motor impulsivity levels (Table 3). ** $p < .001$, * $p < .05$.

Figure 2. Simple slopes probing the interactive effect between attentional and motor impulsivity on perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation. Scores on attentional impulsivity negatively related to perceived self-regulatory success in weight regulation at high scores on motor impulsivity (+1 *SD*), but not at low scores on motor impulsivity (-1 *SD*).

